

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

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Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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Public Executive Summary of Deliverable D5.5

Novel opportunities

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Executive summary log

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Main achievements/outcomes

This Deliverable D5.5 contains information about the identification and evaluation of novel opportunities using OXIPRO-developed enzymes or concepts that were explored outside the four core innovation cases in the project. In Work Package 5, Task 5.5, several concepts were evaluated, first conceptually and then, if merited with laboratory validation. Drawing inspiration from previous work in WP5 and from learnings in recent literature, new opportunities were considered.

Seven ideas or concepts have been considered for enzyme application in various sectors, including textiles, food production and processing, sanitization and cleaning, and personal care. All ideas have been evaluated in a systemic way. Two ideas were considered negative based on lack of technical or commercial feasibility, and not further supported. Five of the seven ideas were considered promising, and further research with literature or experimental data. Of these, one of the concepts stands out as unique and promising, and will be exploited in new project opportunities ahead. The concepts are thus not disclosed in this summary, but an example is provided below to illustrate the approach undertaken.

It was established in the innovation cases in Task 5.1-5.4 that oxidoreductase-driven *in situ* hydrogen peroxide generation alone was not sufficient to achieve the desired effects in those cases. Task 5.5 therefore wished to explore the opportunity to directing more enzyme to the target site to optimize the catalytic efficiency and reduce off-target activity and resource loss. The strategy is that, by adding a protein domain that would lead to binding or interaction, lower doses of enzyme and concentrated

generation of hydrogen peroxide near the target site could be achieved. This approach proved only partially successful in the innovation case, even though it could be demonstrated that hydrogen peroxide forming enzymes were targeted to the specific site, the levels of hydrogen peroxide produced remained insufficient to achieve a successful effect from a commercial standpoint. The Task 5.5 therefore expanded into studies of how to make use of the generated hydrogen peroxide by use of enzymes which can convert it into more radical reactive oxygen species (ROS). This approach, while requiring a second enzyme, looks promising from a technical standpoint because these ROS derivatives appear to be much more effective than hydrogen peroxide alone.